

An Investigation into Students' and Teachers' Perceptions of the Factors Motivating High School Students to Participate in English Classes at International Schools in Istanbul

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Abstract: Motivating students to participate and engage in English classes has recently become a key interest of research as student motivation is a common problem English language instructors face in the language classroom. Although there is much research on learners' attitudes towards student motivation and engagement, teachers' perceptions of the research topic are not available in the literature. This study aims to explore students' and teachers' perceptions of motivating students to participate in English classes at international schools in Istanbul. To achieve the objectives of the research, a mixed-methods research design involving the elements of qualitative and quantitative data has been conducted. A questionnaire in which 100 students and 109 teachers have participated has been undertaken at two international schools in İstanbul. The findings of the study demonstrate that both students and teachers perceive teacher personality and teaching skills as the most important motivational factors. The results also show that there is a difference between students and teachers' perceptions of impacts of the integrative factors, teachers' praise, self-confidence and course-specific factors. However, as far as the demographic variables are concerned, the results reveal that there is no significant difference between teachers' demographic variables and their perceptions of the motivational factors. For example, teachers' perceptions of the motivational factors do not change, considering different age groups. Some recommendations about the ways to motivate students to participate and engage in English classes have been made

Keywords: Motivation, Personality, Skills, Self-Confidence, Praise.

1. INTRODUCTION

The nature and role of motivation in education has been researched by many theorists and practitioners. Historically speaking, motivation has a deep relationship with psychology. As Weiner (1990) describes the relationship between motivation and psychology, "Initially, the experimental study of motivation (the Latin root of *motive* means to move) is linked with the search for the motors of behaviour" (p. 617). He associates motivation with psychological concepts, such as instinct, drive, arousal, need and energisation. Achievement and behaviour are also other key concepts that have close ties with motivation, especially in the late 1960s. Robbins and Judge (2013) evaluate Maslow's approach to motivation and claim "a person will generally be driven to act not only because of the external factor, but also because he or she has a need to be fulfilled" (p. 203). The following years are considered as a continuation of the dominant theoretical approaches in the 1970s. As Weiner (1990) summarises the topics covered by Ball (1982), "Attribution theory, achievement motivation, anxiety, self-esteem, curiosity and, to a much lesser extent, level of aspiration, affiliation, biochemical correlation of motivation, and reinforcement" (p. 620). Since 1990, motivation has been investigated according to topics,

such as casual attributions, self-efficacy, individual differences, anxiety about failure, competitive versus cooperative contexts, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, and praise. In short, theories on motivation should assume that motivation is constant, never ending, fluctuating, and complex, and that it is an almost universal characteristic of practically every human being (Maslow, 1987).

Theorists and scholars working in the field of language learning have been preoccupied with the analysis of phases which second language acquisition (SLA) motivation has gone through for over six decades. The first pioneers, who have paved the way for much research about the first phase, are Robert Gardner and Wallace Lambert (1959) in Canada, where they investigated the relationship between social-psychological effects of second language learning (SLL) and motivation. Social psychological perspectives on language learning motivation emphasise the role of learners' social context and social interactions. Ushioda and Dörnyei (2012) explored the relationship between motivation to acquire a second language and motivation to learn a school subject and said "... learners are expected not simply to acquire knowledge of the language but to identify with the target language community and adopt their distinctive speech behaviours and styles" (p. 396). The second phase, which Dörnyei calls 'the cognitive-situated period of motivation' which is based on the cognitive theories in educational psychology in specific settings like the classroom. In this period, According to Brown (2006), "Motivation places much more emphasis on the individual's decisions..." (p. 168). The decisions may include the specific goals that will be approached or the degree of effort that will be put into by the individual. The third phase which is called the 'process-oriented phase' depends on the motivational change. To further clarify, student motivation is not stable; it can change over periods of time. The fourth phase which is called the 'socio-dynamic phase' focuses on the dynamic nature of motivation. That is, there is a tendency to study this field in the context of self and identity. In addition to its dynamic nature, Al-Hoorie (2017) points out that motivation to learn English is "witnessing the emergence of various themes, such as the affective, unconscious and long-term aspects" (p. 1). However, there is a consensus among theorists and scholars that L2 motivation is global, a multifaceted rather than a uniform variable and no available theory has yet managed to represent it in its total complexity (Dörnyei, 1998).

Motivation for participation in English classes has recently attracted more attention. Classroom participation is a result of good learning and teaching. Dancer and Kamvounias (2005), who have done research into the relationship between motivation and participation, indicate that there are five aspects of this process: preparation, contribution to discussion, group skills, communication skills and attendance. In order to increase participation in language classrooms, communicative language teaching (CLT) emphasises the role of in-class group discussion in fluency development. Wade (1994) suggests that an ideal classroom is a classroom where all learners learn, discuss ideas with their group, participate in the whole-class discussion and listen to other contributions made by other learners. Thus, motivation and participation are two important concepts that cannot be separated from each other. The study carried out by Tasgin and Tunc (2018) shows that there is a strong relationship between motivation and participation in class. They also say that motivation is the force that drives students' participation. In brief, this section has reviewed definition, promotion of classroom participation and the relationship between motivation and participation.

There are some researchers who have conducted research on different types of motivation. One of the distinctions made is identified as integrative and instrumental motivation. Gardner and Lambert (1972) tell the difference between integrative and instrumental motivation. Integrative motivation presents the desire to integrate and communicate with the culture and society of the target language. However, through instrumental motivation, students learn a language to attain instrumental advantages such as getting a better job (Hudson, 2000). Another distinction is made between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. While "intrinsically motivated behaviours are aimed at bringing about certain internally rewarding consequences, namely, feelings of competence and self-determination" (Deci, 1975, as cited in Brown, 2006), extrinsically motivated behaviours are fuelled by rewards from outside, such as grades or job promotion (Harmer, 2007).

Statement of Research Problem

For many years, a great wealth of theoretical studies has been conducted on the factors that motivate students to learn English. However, a large number of students in Turkey learn English without having the motivation to participate in English classes. The study conducted by Akay (2017) about Turkish high school students' demotivation in English classes reveals that their motivation decreases most in high school period. Moreover, most of the research conducted on L2 motivation in the literature only explores students' perceptions of motivational factors to participate. There is not much research investigating teachers' views in the Turkish

context. This is a big gap that needs to be filled in the literature. Furthermore, there is an overall lack of research regarding how to investigate students' and teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes, as stated earlier. In this regard, Le (2020) declares "there is no study which looks at teachers' and students' perceptions together although English classroom is deniably a co-production between teacher and students" (p. 2). Therefore, this study is carried out with an attempt to shed lights on learners' and teachers' views of the factors motivating students to participate in English classes. The second attempt is to find out any possible mismatches between the perceptions of these two groups.

Aims and Questions of the Study

As there is not much research into students' and teachers' attitudes towards motivational factors, this study aims to explore these two groups' perceptions of the factors that motivate high school students at the age of 18 to participate in English classes in international schools in Istanbul. The first objective is to identify students' and teachers' perceptions of motivational factors. The meaning of motivation and the influence of motivational factors on students and teachers are investigated. The second objective is to evaluate students' and teachers' perceptions of motivational variables. The effectiveness of these variables is evaluated, too. The third objective is to compare and contrast these perceptions to find out if there are any similarities and differences. In short, this paper aims to identify, evaluate and analyse the perceptions of the aforementioned two groups.

This study addresses the following research questions:

1. How do international high school students see student motivation to participate in English classes?
2. What are the most important factors that motivate students to participate in English classes?
3. What is the relationship between teachers' demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and their perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes?
4. How do international high school teachers see student motivation to participate in English classes?
5. Is there a difference between international high school students' and their teachers' perceptions of student motivation?

Statement of Rationale and Significance

The reasons for conducting this study are as follows. The first reason is to identify the factors that influence students' motivation to participate in English classes and find the most effective ones in Turkish context. The second reason is to prove or disapprove the hypothesis that high school teachers have a very important role in motivating their students to participate. The third reason is to investigate high school students' perceptions of motivational factors and learn to what extent they are motivated. The fourth reason is to examine the relationship between teachers' demographic variables and their perceptions of the factors motivating their students to participate. The last reason is to explore the relationship between motivational factors and participation that leads to successful language learning.

The study results are expected to make significant contributions to the relationship between motivation and foreign language learning and teaching. Initially, the findings provide valuable data regarding students' and teachers' perceptions of the factors motivating students to participate in English classes. In addition, they add to the growing research concerning teachers' perceptions of these factors. They contribute to literature by bridging any possible gaps between students' and teachers' perceptions of motivational factors as well. Furthermore, they offer insights into the area of how to enhance student motivation for participating in English lessons depending on their attitudes. The study, therefore, has significant implications for the Turkish educational context, especially students within the international school context.

2. METHODOLOGY

Setting and Participants

This research which aims at identifying students' and teachers' perceptions of motivation was conducted at two private international schools located on the European side of Istanbul, Turkey. The first school is Alfayez International School in Bağcılar in Istanbul. The students are from more than 34 nationalities. The programmes offered at this school teach Arabic and English (Cambridge Programme) where education starts from kindergarten to twelfth grade. When students graduate from high school, they get their certificates that are accredited by the Turkish Ministry of National Education

and the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The second school is Aljazari International School of Science and Technology in Küçükçekmeçe in Istanbul. The students and staff are from different nationalities with more than 1280 students and 1180 staff. As the curriculum of Aljazari school is concerned, students have the chance to access a meaningful and high-quality American curriculum by applying the recent methods of teaching. The program offered at this school starts from kindergarten until grade 12 (age 18).

Two different groups of research participants are selected for the study. The first group of participants are international high school teachers who have agreed to participate in this study. This group consists of 109 participants with different qualifications and teaching experience. The target group consists of a total of 50 male and 59 female EFL instructors. The demographic data concerning age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience are collected through an online survey and analysed statistically, using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The second group of participants are international high school students who are at the age of 18 and who have agreed to participate in the study. This group of respondents consists of 100 students who have been learning in international schools for at least one year. which makes them knowledgeable about the school and the teaching context. The students also have sufficient knowledge of English, which makes students able to respond to the statements in the questionnaire. Furthermore, there are two main types of sampling: probability and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling, the respondents are chosen randomly to take part in a survey or a questionnaire. Every respondent has an equal chance of being selected for a study. The probability that a random individual can take part in a study should be taken into consideration by the researcher (Pace, 2021). However, a non-probability sampling is adopted in the current study, which means that the respondents are chosen by voluntary sampling depending on conditions of availability, accessibility and convenience (Taherdoost, 2016).

Data Collection Instruments

Two data gathering tools involving an online questionnaire for teachers and an online questionnaire for students have been adopted in this study. In fact, while quantitative data are collected through the statements in both questionnaires, qualitative data are collected through one open-ended research question in both questionnaires. Richards (2014) declares that quantitative and qualitative data do not present different worlds. They are different ways of recording observations of the same world. Likewise, as Dörnyei (2007) notes, "In most cases a mixed methods approach can offer additional benefits for the understanding of the phenomenon in question" (p. 47). Consequently, he advises PhD students to try and integrate quantitative and qualitative methods in their studies. As far as this study is concerned, both research instruments will provide information about students' and teachers' perceptions of the motivational factors to participate in English classes. For example, the statements in the questionnaires will give insights into how students and teachers view motivational factors. The open-ended question will also shed light on the most important factors. Additionally, the research tools will explore the relationship between teachers' demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and their perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes.

Questionnaires

The questionnaire for teachers consists of three parts. The first part involves demographic questions concerning teachers' age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience. The second part of the questionnaire includes 29 statements focusing on the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. They are grouped into nine themes: statements one and two are related to intrinsic factors, statements three and four are related to integrative factors, statements five, six and seven are related to instrumental factors, statements eight and nine are related to the influence of self-confidence, statements from ten to 17 are related to the influence of teachers, statements from 18 to 21 are related to course-specific factors, statements from 22 to 24 are related to classroom-specific factors, statements from 25 to 27 are related to the influence of classmates and statements 28 and 29 are related to the influence of parents. The third part of the questionnaire includes an open-ended question that asks teachers to rank the most important factors from one to three.

The questionnaire for students is prepared with the same structure and content as in the questionnaire for teachers. However, there are two differences between them. The first difference is the subject in each questionnaire statement. That is, the subject in the questionnaire for teachers is 'students'. This subject changes into 'I' in the questionnaire for students. The second difference is that the questionnaire for students does not contain any demographic questions.

Procedure

After getting the original researcher's permission to use her questionnaires, an online questionnaire for teachers and an online questionnaire for students are prepared via 'Google forms'. First, the researcher sends the link of the online questionnaire for teachers to two colleagues teaching at two different international schools in Istanbul. Then, to conduct this study in their schools, each colleague asks the school administration for permission. After getting the permission, the colleagues share the link of the questionnaire with the English teachers in their schools. As far as the questionnaire for students is concerned, the same procedure is followed. The researcher sends the link of the questionnaire to the same two colleagues who, in turn, share the link with the students in their schools.

A questionnaire can be analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics (Field, 2013). To start with, descriptive statistics consists of the measures of central tendency, which is sometimes called measures of central location, and measures of dispersion. While the mean, median and mode are valid measures of central tendency, standard deviation and variance are two most commonly used measures of dispersion. Measures of dispersion are used to describe the extent to which the data are homogenous or heterogeneous. Moreover, inferential statistics, which can be used to generalise the findings from a particular sample to the whole population, tests statistically significant differences in categorical variables and tests statistically significant correlations among continuous variables. The inferential statistical tests are divided into two types: parametric and non-parametric tests, depending on whether or not the data are normally distributed. In this regard, sensitivity analysis can be used because it combines both parametric and non-parametric tests to increase the validity of the collected data. Furthermore, the independent-samples t-test is used to test whether or not there is a statistically significant difference between two categorical variables like gender and students' perceptions. Its non-parametric equivalent is the Mann-Whitney U Test. However, the One-Way Analysis of Variance is used to test whether or not there is a statistically significant difference between more than two groups. Its non-parametric equivalent is the Kruskal Wallis H Test. Likewise, Pearson and Spearman correlation tests are respectively parametric and non-parametric versions of the correlation tests that investigate the association between two or more continuous variables.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings and discussion of research questions are presented in this part.

RQ1: How do international high school students see student motivation to participate in English classes?

Students' perceptions of the motivational factors are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: The Agreement Percentage (%) of Likert Scales in the Questionnaire for Students

		Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. I participate more in class because I am interested in English language.	Count	33	35	28	4
	Row N%	33.0%	35.0%	28.0%	4.0%
2. I participate more in class because I want to enrich my English knowledge.	Count	29	45	20	6
	Row N%	29.0%	45.0%	20.0%	6.0%
3. I participate more in class because I am interested in the cultures of English-speaking countries.	Count	9	31	35	25
	Row N%	9.0%	31.0%	35.0%	25.0%
4. I participate more in class because I want to learn to communicate in English with foreign people.	Count	30	32	27	11
	Row N%	30.0%	32.0%	27.0%	11.0%
5. I participate more in class because I want to get high marks.	Count	46	27	24	3
	Row N%	46.0%	27.0%	24.0%	3.0%
6. I participate more in class because I want to be praised by teacher.	Count	12	26	40	22
	Row N%	12.0%	26.0%	40.0%	22.0%
7. I participate more in class because I want to have a good job in the future.	Count	37	36	17	10
	Row N%	37.0%	36.0%	17.0%	10.0%
8. I participate more in class when I feel confident of language proficiency.	Count	19	43	32	6
	Row N%	19.0%	43.0%	32.0%	6.0%

9. I participate more in class when I do not have language use anxiety.	Count	21	40	31	8
	Row N%	21.0%	40.0%	31.0%	8.0%
10. I participate more in class when teacher is supportive.	Count	57	37	5	1
	Row N%	57.0%	37.0%	5.0%	1.0%
11. I participate more in class when teacher is friendly.	Count	62	35	3	0
	Row N%	62.0%	35.0%	3.0%	0.0%
12. I participate more in class when teacher is enthusiastic.	Count	45	42	11	2
	Row N%	45.0%	42.0%	11.0%	2.0%
13. I participate more in class when teacher gives positive nonverbal behaviours such as smiling.	Count	53	27	17	3
	Row N%	53.0%	27.0%	17.0%	3.0%
14. I participate more in class when teacher shows good classroom management skills.	Count	30	43	25	2
	Row N%	30.0%	43.0%	25.0%	2.0%
15. I participate more in class when teacher shows good communication skills.	Count	41	47	9	3
	Row N%	41.0%	47.0%	9.0%	3.0%
16. I participate more in class when teacher uses exciting teaching techniques.	Count	31	34	32	3
	Row N%	31.0%	34.0%	32.0%	3.0%
17. I participate more in class when teacher gives clear presentation.	Count	30	44	23	3
	Row N%	30.0%	44.0%	23.0%	3.0%
18. I participate more in class when the content of the lesson is relevant to my life.	Count	29	46	19	6
	Row N%	29.0%	46.0%	19.0%	6.0%
19. I participate more in class when the content of the lesson is interesting.	Count	40	39	19	2
	Row N%	40.0%	39.0%	19.0%	2.0%
20. I participate more in class when the content of the lesson is related to cultural issues.	Count	14	32	35	19
	Row N%	14.0%	32.0%	35.0%	19.0%
21. I participate more in class when activities are in diverse forms such as games, role play or presentations.	Count	37	38	20	5
	Row N%	37.0%	38.0%	20.0%	5.0%
22. I participate more in class when the classroom is well-equipped.	Count	25	38	31	6
	Row N%	25.0%	38.0%	31.0%	6.0%
23. I participate more in class when the classroom atmosphere is positive.	Count	48	40	11	1
	Row N%	48.0%	40.0%	11.0%	1.0%
24. I participate more in class when the class size is small.	Count	19	32	34	15
	Row N%	19.0%	32.0%	34.0%	15.0%
25. I participate more in class when classmates are friendly.	Count	55	39	5	1
	Row N%	55.0%	39.0%	5.0%	1.0%
26. I participate more in class when classmates are supportive.	Count	64	28	7	1
	Row N%	64.0%	28.0%	7.0%	1.0%
27. I participate more in class when classmates show no judgement of my opinions.	Count	35	37	23	5
	Row N%	35.0%	37.0%	23.0%	5.0%
28. I participate more in class when I get pressure from my parents.	Count	0	6	29	65
	Row N%	0.0%	6.0%	29.0%	65.0%
29. I participate more in class when I get support from my parents.	Count	43	42	7	8
	Row N%	43.0%	42.0%	7.0%	8.0%

To specify, as can be inferred from the data presented in the table, statements 1 and 2 show that around 70% of the students agree that their participation is affected by the intrinsic factors. They are interested in English language and they want to enrich their English knowledge. Noticeably, 30% of the students are not interested in English language. Statements 3 and 4 indicate that more than half of the students are integratively motivated. The data in these statements reveal that these students want to communicate with the target language community. Just 40% are interested in L2 cultures. Regarding the instrumental factors in statements 5, 6 and 7, the data deduced from these statements demonstrate that 73% of the students participate in English classes to have a good job in the future and to get high marks. The data

also shows that 62% of the students do not consider praise from the teacher as an important factor that motivates them to participate. The figures in statements 8 and 9 indicate that around 61% of the students are motivated to participate when they feel confident of their language proficiency and when they do not have language use anxiety. This clarifies the importance of self-confidence in the engagement in the language learning process.

The statements from 10 to 17 that focus on the influence of teachers show that the vast majority of the students consider the teachers' skills and characters to be important factors that motivate them to participate. They believe that if the teacher is friendly and supportive, they can participate more. In addition, the students emphasise the teachers' communication skills. The data also show that good classroom management skills and presentations are crucial motivational factors. This finding adds up to what has been found by Allum's (2020) finding which proposes that students report teacher characteristics to be the most important motivational factor. This result also affirms Dörnyei and Csizér's (1998) suggestion that developing a good relationship with learners can have a great influence on student motivation and participation. The statements from 18 to 21 are related to course-specific factors. The data in the statements 18, 19 and 21 show that almost 75% of the students agree that when the content of the lesson is interesting and related to their lives and when the activities are presented in a fun way, the students are motivated to participate. However, when the lesson is related to cultural issues, more than half of the students are not motivated to participate.

The statements from 22 to 24 are related to classroom-specific factors. According to the figures in these statements, 88% of the students emphasise the role of the positive atmosphere of the classroom. 63% agree that a well-equipped classroom affects language learning positively. Nearly, half of the students do not consider the small size of the classroom to be an important motivational factor. This is consistent with what has been discussed in the literature review. Effective learning cannot take place unless a positive, pleasant, joyful and supportive atmosphere is created in the class (Al-Ghafri, 2018; Dörnyei, 2001). Concerning the influence of classmates in the statements 25, 26 and 27, the vast majority of the students agree that classmates play an important role in active participation in the class. On the other hand, 28% of the participants believe that classmates' judgements are important for engagement in the class. This finding corresponds with what Little (2004) and Wade (1994) state that learners become motivated to participate in the language learning process when they work collaboratively and cooperatively with their classmates. Little states that when learners are motivated and work cooperatively in the class, they have a better chance of becoming autonomous learners. In addition, this result is in parallel with what has been found by a study conducted in Malaysia on undergraduate students who point out that classmates can be a motivational factor to actively engage in the learning activities (Mustapha, Rahman & Yunus, 2010).

Finally, the data in the statements 28 and 29 indicate that nearly most students do not agree with the idea that pressure from parents motivates them to participate in the class. At the same time, these students demonstrate that support and careful instruction from parents can greatly influence their success in the language learning process. This finding is similar to the study conducted by Leahy (2017), in which the parental influence is considered to be the biggest reason for learning English. Overall, this finding is similar to Yılmaz et al.'s (2017) finding in which parent involvement has less effect on students' success than the influence of teachers.

RQ2: What are the most important factors that motivate students to participate in English classes?

The second research question investigates students' views of the most important three factors. Similar to what has been found in the first research question, students consider the friendly and enthusiastic teacher as the first and second most important factors respectively. This once again affirms the vital role that teachers play in motivating students to participate. More precisely, the results show that students perceive teacher's personality to be more important than the teacher's teaching skills. The third most important factor according to students is the supportive classmates. This also affirms the second most important statement in research question one. Thus, students' focus on the influence of teachers' characters and the influence of classmates may be attributed to that because of the international pandemic Covid-19, some face-to-face classes have been cancelled and online classes have taken place instead. To cope with the new situation, more cooperation between teachers and students and among students themselves has become essential.

Surprisingly, the students in this study do not tend to favour instrumental factors, such as getting better marks or getting a good job in the future. This finding contrasts with what has been found by Le (2020), who has explored high school students' motivational factors in state schools in Vietnam. In her study, students consider the instrumental variables as the most important factors that motivate them to participate in English classes. This opinion also contradicts what has been found by Svobodová's (2015) finding that the factors which are recognised by the students to be the most influential

belong to the category of instrumental factors. In a similar vein, the findings in this study show that students are not interested in the integrative factors. This is also in contrast with Le's study which demonstrates that students consider the integrative factors to be the third most important motivational factor. However, the results in this study and Le's show that students do not perceive intrinsic factors as important motivational factors.

RQ3: What is the relationship between teachers' demographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and their perceptions of student motivation to participate in English classes?

The number of teachers who have participated in the study is 109 teachers. The following table shows the demographic information of the teacher respondents as frequencies and percentages.

Table 2: Sociodemographic Variables

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	22-25	25	22.9	22.9	22.9
	26-29	22	20.2	20.2	43.1
	30-33	17	15.6	15.6	58.7
	34-37	14	12.8	12.8	71.6
	38- more	28	25.7	25.7	97.2
	41	1	.9	.9	98.2
	50	1	.9	.9	99.1
	Older	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	109	100.0	100.0	
Gender	Female	59	54.1	54.1	54.1
	Male	50	45.9	45.9	100.0
	Total	109	100.0	100.0	
Qualifications	BA	38	34.9	34.9	34.9
	CELTA	6	5.5	5.5	40.4
	DELTA	1	.9	.9	41.3
	M.A	47	43.1	43.1	84.4
	Other	1	.9	.9	85.3
	Ph.D.	10	9.2	9.2	94.5
	TESOL	6	5.5	5.5	100.0
Total	109	100.0	100.0		
Teaching experience	1-3	38	34.9	34.9	34.9
	4-6	23	21.1	21.1	56.0
	7-9	11	10.1	10.1	66.1
	10 and more	37	33.9	33.9	100.0
	Total	109	100.0	100.0	

As can be seen from the table, while 43% of the participants are between 22 and 29 years old, nearly 28.5% of them are between 30 and 37 years old. Thus, 72% of the teachers are between 22 and 37 years old. As far as the gender is concerned, more than half of the respondents are female novice teachers with one to three years of teaching experience. Female teachers constitute 54.1% of the sample, whereas male respondents constitute 45.9% of the sample. In terms of experience, 34.9% of the respondents have between one and three years of experience. Regarding the qualifications, the majority of the respondents have a master's degree (43.1%). In brief, no statistically significant difference is found between the different sociodemographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and the teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. This means that the findings cannot be generalised from the sample in this study to the whole population. However, there are slight differences in favour of young and novice male teachers in terms of their agreement with the most statements in the questionnaire for teachers.

RQ4: How do international high school teachers see student motivation to participate in English classes?

Teachers' perceptions of the motivational factors are presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: The Agreement Percentage (%) of Likert Scales in the Questionnaire for Teachers

		Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Students participate more in class because they are interested in English language.	Count	25	47	34	3
	Row N%	22.9%	43.1%	31.2%	2.8%
2. Students participate more in class because they want to enrich their English knowledge.	Count	27	50	28	4
	Row N%	24.8%	45.9%	25.7%	3.7%
3. Students participate more in class because they are interested in the cultures of English-speaking countries.	Count	15	33	44	17
	Row N%	13.8%	30.3%	40.4%	15.6%
4. Students participate more in class because they want to learn to communicate in English with foreign people.	Count	44	44	16	5
	Row N%	40.4%	40.4%	14.7%	4.6%
5. Students participate more in class because they want to get high marks.	Count	42	34	25	8
	Row N%	38.5%	31.2%	22.9%	7.3%
6. Students participate more in class because they want to be praised by teacher.	Count	22	39	30	18
	Row N%	20.2%	35.8%	27.5%	16.5%
7. Students participate more in class because they want to have a good job in the future.	Count	38	35	26	10
	Row N%	34.9%	32.1%	23.9%	9.2%
8. Students participate more in class when they feel confident of their language proficiency.	Count	43	34	21	11
	Row N%	39.4%	31.2%	19.3%	10.1%
9. Students participate more in class when they do not have language use anxiety.	Count	36	44	22	7
	Row N%	33.0%	40.4%	20.2%	6.4%
10. Students participate more in class when teacher is supportive.	Count	68	30	8	3
	Row N%	62.4%	27.5%	7.3%	2.8%
11. Students participate more in class when teacher is friendly.	Count	67	35	4	3
	Row N%	61.5%	32.1%	3.7%	2.8%
12. Students participate more in class when teacher is enthusiastic.	Count	67	35	5	2
	Row N%	61.5%	32.1%	4.6%	1.8%
13. Students participate more in class when teacher gives positive nonverbal behaviours such as smiling.	Count	54	46	5	4
	Row N%	49.5%	42.2%	4.6%	3.7%
14. Students participate more in class when teacher shows good classroom management skills.	Count	63	38	7	1
	Row N%	57.8%	34.9%	6.4%	0.9%
15. Students participate more in class when teacher shows good communication skills.	Count	65	34	8	2
	Row N%	59.6%	31.2%	7.3%	1.8%
16. Students participate more in class when teacher uses exciting teaching skills.	Count	70	31	6	2
	Row N%	64.2%	28.4%	5.5%	1.8%
17. Students participate more in class when teacher gives clear presentation.	Count	44	52	11	2
	Row N%	40.4%	47.7%	10.1%	1.8%
18. Students participate more in class when the content of the lesson is relevant to their lives.	Count	54	42	8	5
	Row N%	49.5%	38.5%	7.4%	4.6%
19. Students participate more in class when the content of the lesson is interesting.	Count	61	41	5	2
	Row N%	56.0%	37.6%	4.6%	1.8%
20. Students participate more in class when the content of the lesson is related to cultural issues.	Count	28	36	38	7
	Row N%	25.7%	33.0%	34.9%	6.4%

21. Students participate more in class when activities are in diverse forms such as games, role play or presentations.	Count	63	35	10	1
	Row N%	57.8%	32.1%	9.2%	0.9%
22. Students participate more in class when the classroom is well-equipped.	Count	34	45	26	4
	Row N%	31.2%	41.2%	23.9%	3.7%
23. Students participate more in class when the classroom atmosphere is positive.	Count	64	35	7	3
	Row N%	58.7%	32.1%	6.4%	2.8%
24. Students participate more in class when the classroom size is small.	Count	21	33	32	23
	Row N%	19.3%	30.2%	29.4%	21.1%
25. Students participate more in class when classmates are friendly.	Count	43	53	12	1
	Row N%	39.4%	48.7%	11.0%	0.9%
26. Students participate more in class when classmates are supportive.	Count	50	43	13	3
	Row N%	45.9%	39.4%	11.9%	2.8%
27. Students participate more in class when classmates show no judgment of their opinions.	Count	50	39	14	6
	Row N%	45.9%	35.8%	12.8%	5.5%
28. Students participate more in class when they get pressure from their parents.	Count	11	18	38	42
	Row N%	10.1%	16.5%	34.9%	38.5%
29. Students participate more in class when they get support from their parents.	Count	47	43	17	2
	Row N%	43.1%	39.4%	15.6%	1.8%

As seen in the table, around 68% of the teachers in the statements 1 and 2 believe that the intrinsic factors have an important role in motivating students to participate in English classes. The students are more interested in enriching their English knowledge than in English language itself. Noticeably, one-third of the respondents state that the students are not interested in English language. According to the figures in statements 3 and 4, the belief that the students are influenced by integrative factors is shared by nearly 62% of the teachers. The teachers believe that the students learn English to communicate with the target community. However, 56% of the respondents demonstrate that the cultures of English-speaking countries are not perceived to be an important factor in student motivation to participate.

Concerning the instrumental factors in the statements from 5 to 7, the belief that the students are influenced by the instrumental factors is held by 64% of the teachers. According to teachers' beliefs, the important instrumental factors that motivate students to participate are listed as 1) getting high marks, 2) having a good job in the future, and 3) being praised by the teacher. However, 44% of the teachers believe that being praised by teacher is not an important motivational factor that has an impact on student participation. Statements 8 and 9 are related to the influence of self-confidence. The data show that around 73% of the teachers claim that self-confidence plays an important role in motivating students to participate. They also believe that when students do not have language-use anxiety, they are more engaged in the language learning process.

Regarding the statements from 10 to 17 that focus on the influence of teachers, the vast majority of the teachers believe that the teacher assumes critical significance in motivating students to participate. The respondents demonstrate that if the teacher is friendly and enthusiastic, the students are more motivated. This finding is consistent with Renandya's (2014) study in the literature review, suggesting that enthusiastic teachers can make their teaching active, motivating and enjoyable. Besides, a friendly teacher is considered as an important factor. This can also be linked with what has been found and stated in a previous study in which having a friendly relationship with students is considered a precondition for student motivation in the class (Alrabai, 2016). Furthermore, teachers' teaching skills play a vital role in motivating students. This finding corroborates what has been supposed by Dörnyei (2001a) and Renandya (2014) that using practical and appropriate teaching methods can increase student motivation. Moreover, teachers show their interest in implementing good classroom management skills. The importance of management skills is supported in the studies of Richards (1990) and Yılmaz et al. (2017) as mentioned in the chapter of literature review. In addition, teachers also emphasise the role of showing good communication skills in the classroom. This concept concurs with Ochoa et al.'s (2016) finding in the chapter of literature review in which teachers perceive communicative activities to be an important motivational factor.

Data in statements from 18 to 21 show that 82.5% of the teachers affirm the importance of course-specific factors in student engagement in language learning process. Among these variables, they believe that the most important factor is the statement 19 which states that students participate more when the content of the lesson is interesting. This finding is in agreement with previous studies of Dörnyei (1994) and Renandya (2014), in which interesting activities in the classroom are seen as critical factors for effective teaching. However, 41% do not consider the cultural issues as a significant factor in motivating students to participate. 70% of the respondents agree that the importance of classroom-related factors is undeniable. The vast majority of teachers direct attention toward the role of a positive atmosphere in the class in motivating students to participate. This idea can be contextualised within Al-Ghafri (2018) and Dörnyei's (2001a) studies in which they suggest that effective teaching cannot take place unless a positive, pleasant, joyful and supportive atmosphere is created in the class as mentioned in the literature review. Remarkably, around half of the teachers do not see the small size of the class as an affective motivational factor in student participation.

As can be seen from the statements from 25 to 27, the majority of teachers support the idea that classmates have a great influence on student motivation to participate. They stress the importance of classmates' characters in motivating students. Just 18% agree that classmates' judgement of their peers' opinions can influence student motivation to participate. Finally, three-quarters of the teacher respondents disagree with the item 28 suggesting that pressure from parents makes students participate more. On the other hand, 82.5% agree that support and careful attention from parents can motivate students to participate effectively. The same result is found in Le's (2020) study in which the majority of teachers disagree that pressure from parents can have positive impacts on student participation in the class.

RQ5: Is there a difference between international high school students' and their teachers' perceptions of student motivation?

Table 4: The Correlation between Students' and Teachers' Responses to Likert Scale Statements

Pearson Correlation	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
.154	58	.126

The last research question explores participants' responses to know whether there is a difference between international high school students' and teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. The table indicates that there is a weak positive correlation between the students' and teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. This means that significant differences between these two groups' perceptions can be noted. The results of this study demonstrate that students' and teachers' perceptions are most significantly different when observing the impacts of the integrative factor (learning English to communicate with foreign people), teachers' praises, self-confidence (language- use anxiety) and course-specific factors (statements 19 and 21). The findings show that students' motivation to participate in English classes is less affected by these factors than what teachers think. Thus, it can be said that there a weak positive correlation between the students' and teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. This finding corresponds with what has been found in Le's (2020) study in which there is no total agreement between students' and teachers' perceptions of some motivational factors.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following can be deduced. Students consider the friendly and enthusiastic teacher as the most important motivational factor. Regarding the demographic variables, there is no statistically significant difference between the different sociodemographic variables (age, gender, qualifications and teaching experience) and the teachers' perceptions of the factors that motivate students to participate in English classes. Similar to students' perceptions of the most important factor, teachers perceive the influence of teacher to be the most important factor in student motivation and participation. Finally, the findings show that there is no total agreement between students' and teachers' perceptions of the motivational factors. That is, students' and teachers' perceptions are most significantly different when observing the impacts of the integrative factor (learning English to communicate with foreign people), teachers' praises, self-confidence (language- use anxiety) and course-specific factors.

Taking the findings of this study into consideration, some suggestions can be made to researchers for future studies. Firstly, this study can be limited since a questionnaire for students and a questionnaire for teachers have been conducted.

Therefore, further research can be conducted using other data collection instruments, such as classroom observation and individual interviews with students and teachers to have a thorough understanding of students' and teachers' perceptions of the motivational factors. Moreover, the present study has been conducted only at two international private schools in Istanbul. Thus, further research can explore students' and teachers' perceptions in a more general setting where more schools can be included in the study. In addition, the same topic can be carried out in different contexts, such as at secondary schools, universities or university preparatory schools. Finally, the same study can be conducted in other countries to have more findings about the issue.

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